

SOME ASPECTS OF PROVIDING PERSONNEL STABILITY IN INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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ANNOTATION. In the article, the content of the activities related to the selection and placement of candidates for the service of the internal affairs bodies and ensuring the stability of personnel, as well as the issue of selecting candidates for the service of the internal affairs bodies, the opinions on whether to search for personnel from among the candidates who have been positively described in the armed forces and have served and released to the reserve of the armed forces given Problems related to the process of selecting personnel for the service of internal affairs bodies, relevant regulatory and legal documents were analyzed, proposals and recommendations for improving the field were developed.

Keywords: personnel, candidate, selection, personnel selection, personnel training, personnel reserve, personnel placement.

It is not without reason that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, emphasized that “the issue of personnel is our future, our tomorrow.” Indeed, our tomorrow, our future, and the place of our country in the world community certainly depend on what kind of personnel we select, train, and place in the right places.

Because the correct selection and placement of personnel serves as a guarantee of the effective functioning of production (operation).

The issue of selecting candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies has been considered urgent from the beginning. Based on the shortcomings made in the process of selecting personnel over the years, based on the experience gained and efforts aimed at minimizing the human factor in the selection, and as a result, the relevant regulatory and legal documents are being improved.

The personnel selection stage is the process of studying candidates and determining their ability to perform their duties in certain positions. For example, the candidate's knowledge, profession, work skills, and personal characteristics are studied. These qualities are checked to see if the candidate meets the requirements for a particular position.

The main direction of administrative reforms in our country is to ensure the transparency of the activities of the executive authorities, while our citizens should have the opportunity to receive relevant information about the activities of the executive authorities. In particular, citizens should be provided with access to information about the activities of the internal affairs bodies. For example, citizens should have information about the requirements for candidates and the level of legal and social guarantees¹.

¹ Bobrov A.M. Nekotorye aspekty obespecheniya dostupa k informatsii o deyatelnosti organov vnutrennix del Rossiyskoy Federatsii // Administrativnoe pravo i protsessii. 2011. No.10. P.27).

N.I. Razuvaeva expressed her reasonable opinion that the personnel selection process is a complex one and that candidates should be selected in the following stages:

- 1) searching for candidates;
- 2) studying candidates, assessing their personal and professional qualities;
- 3) considering the issue of appointing candidates to positions or having them participate in the competition based on the results of the study;
- 4) conducting a competition to identify the most worthy candidates².

Indeed, worthy candidates are first sought from exemplary families, neighborhoods, educational institutions, and government organizations, and only after they are comprehensively studied, a conclusion is made as to whether they are worthy or unworthy of serving in the internal affairs bodies in the future, in accordance with the relevant selection criteria. Therefore, the successful selection of candidates for the service of internal affairs bodies also depends on the chosen search method.

Usually, candidates for the service of internal affairs bodies apply voluntarily, mainly through advertisements in the mass media, on the Internet, in relevant state organizations, institutions and enterprises, and among graduates of civil higher educational institutions, or for other reasons (relatives serving, a desire to wear service uniforms from a young age, provision with a stable monthly salary).

In our opinion, it is necessary to determine the motive for entering the service from any candidate who applies to the territorial internal affairs bodies during the interview. Because it is precisely through this motive that it is possible to assess and predict the candidate's future service activities in some sense. For example, during the interview, there is a significant difference between candidates who express a narrow worldview, simply interested in wearing service uniforms, and those who express a desire to maintain the peace and tranquility of citizens.

According to the results of a survey conducted among some candidates entering the internal affairs bodies (456 people) to determine their motives, 48.2% of respondents indicated a desire to ensure the order established by law, the rights and freedoms and security of citizens, 84.2% of respondents noted the presence of financial stability, 62.7% of respondents noted the provision of social guarantees and benefits, 34% of respondents noted a family tradition, and 71.7% of respondents noted an interest in the profession.

Thus, the majority of candidates expressed their desire to work in the internal affairs bodies due to the provision of financial stability, social guarantees and benefits.

In our opinion, it is necessary to select candidates, first of all, based on appropriate criteria, starting from preschool education, secondary school, and to implement targeted measures in agreement with their parents and with the help of relevant specialists, while raising them in a spirit of high patriotism. It is also advisable to search for personnel for internal affairs bodies among candidates who have a positive reputation and have served in the armed forces and have been released into the armed forces reserve.

² Razuvaeva N.I. Selection and attestation of personnel of internal organs (administrative-legal and organizational aspects). *dis. sugar walk nauk Voronezh*, 2014. –215 str., Upravlenie personalom : uchebnik dlya vuzov / Pod editor. T. Yu. Bazarova, B.L. Eremina, 2002. P. 213

We also believe that it is necessary to consider the candidacies of former employees of the internal affairs bodies who were dismissed from service at their own request or under non-negative circumstances (due to staff reductions, etc.), but who possess professional and personal qualities.

Article 26, Chapter 6 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" dated September 16, 2016 stipulates that citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan aged eighteen to thirty years, including thirty years, who have the appropriate education, and who are capable of performing the duties of an internal affairs officer due to their personal and professional qualities, state of health, and physical fitness, shall be admitted to service in the internal affairs bodies on a voluntary basis, on a competitive basis³.

The Order of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2022 No. 52 "On approval of the Instruction on the procedure for organizing and conducting selection events for candidates for service in the Internal Affairs bodies"⁴ approved the Instruction "On the procedure for organizing and conducting selection events for candidates for service in the Internal Affairs bodies". This Order consists of 7 chapters and 91 clauses, which establish the procedure and rules for organizing selection events, preliminary study of candidates, assessment of the level of physical fitness of candidates, assessment of the level of intellectual development and psycho-emotional stability of candidates, and conducting a final interview.

This instruction only establishes the procedure for organizing and conducting selection events for candidates who apply to serve in the internal affairs bodies, but does not specify where to look for or methods for searching for suitable candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies.

Therefore, in our opinion, there is a need to develop an Instruction "On the procedure for selecting suitable candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies, primarily from preschool and secondary schools, as well as higher educational institutions and relevant labor collectives, and for implementing systematic measures with them".

Candidates selected for service in the internal affairs bodies shall serve as employees of the internal affairs bodies in accordance with the Regulations "On the Procedure for Service in the Internal Affairs Bodies", approved by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3413 dated November 29, 2017 "On Measures to Radically Improve the Procedure for Working with Personnel of the Internal Affairs Bodies and Organizing Their Service"⁵. This Regulation consists of 12 chapters and 164 paragraphs, which regulate the procedures for admission to service in the internal affairs bodies, awarding and depriving them of special titles, appointment to positions, dismissal from positions and rotation, training, retraining and advanced training of employees, transfer of service to other state bodies and organizations upon selection (appointment, mobilization), certification, vacations, legal and social protection, service regime, extension of service, dismissal from service and reinstatement, and final rules.

³ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" of September 16, 2016

⁴ Order No. 52 of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2022 "On approval of the instruction on the procedure for organizing and holding events for the selection of candidates for service in internal affairs bodies

⁵ Resolution No. 3413 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the procedure for working with personnel of internal affairs bodies and organizing their service

We believe that it would be appropriate to review the relevant criteria for evaluating the performance of employees selected and serving in the internal affairs bodies, as well as the mechanism for encouraging them based on their service and gradually moving up the service ladder.

According to the analysis of statistical data, in 2021, the number of people admitted to the internal affairs bodies increased by two and a half times compared to 2018.

It is necessary to determine exactly what factors this indicator is related to. For example, the creation of additional jobs due to population growth, an increase in service responsibilities, or an increase in the number of dismissals, etc.

Analyzing statistical indicators of employees dismissed from internal affairs bodies in 2018-2021, it can be seen that there is almost no change. However, in 2018, the number of people dismissed from service in the internal affairs bodies was 58 percent more than the number of those accepted for service, and by 2021, on the contrary, the number of people accepted for service in the internal affairs bodies was almost twice as much as those dismissed.

It can be observed that in 2021, the number of officers, sergeants and officers dismissed from internal affairs bodies due to negative reasons has almost halved compared to 2018.

It is somewhat alarming that the number of employees dismissed from internal affairs bodies at their own request in 2021 is almost twice as high as in 2018.

If we analyze the vacancies in the internal affairs bodies, we can see that in 2021 this indicator increased by almost 10% compared to 2018, and this is also a matter of concern in our opinion.

Employees who resigned from the internal affairs bodies at their own request indicated the following as the reason for their dismissal:

1. The lack of a set working time for internal affairs officers. However, Article 30, Chapter 6 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" dated September 16, 2016 states that "The working time of internal affairs officers may not exceed forty hours per week";
2. The increase in the workload of employees, the uneven distribution of official duties among them, and their involvement in work that is not part of their official duties (excessive business trips, participation in working groups exceeding the norm, seasonal work in the field, improvement work in neighborhoods, etc.);
3. Due to the lack of clear criteria for encouraging or punishing employees based on their service, some managers make incorrect decisions based on their subjective approach in this regard;
4. Insufficient individual psychological contact between the employee and the manager (disagreement);
5. Due to health problems due to work or because the monthly salary is not enough to live on (for the family), etc.

In order for employees of the internal affairs bodies to perform their duties in a stable manner, we believe that it is advisable to eliminate the above-mentioned problems and fully implement the incentive provisions⁶ on social support and guarantees for employees in the relevant existing regulatory documents.

⁶ Resolution No. 3216 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of training, retraining and professional development of employees of internal affairs bodies

In addition, today the system for forming a reserve of personnel and leadership personnel in the internal affairs bodies, as well as the institute of mentoring, cannot be said to be up to the required level.

One of the urgent issues for the internal affairs bodies is the training of professional leadership personnel and the creation of their reserve.

By 2021, a number of problems were identified in the training of leadership personnel at the Academy. That is, there were many cases where local recruiting bodies sent candidates to the Academy who were not included in the reserve of leadership personnel by the personnel department⁷ and who could not be a sufficient example for other employees with their professional qualities, moral appearance, behavior and level of culture⁸. Most surprisingly, the selection for admission to the Academy was in many cases limited to candidates of this category, that is, those who did not meet the requirements for future leadership personnel. As a result, the majority of students who entered the Academy not only violated the established order and discipline at the Academy, but also poorly mastered the subjects, which is completely contrary to the policy of training leadership personnel in the IAS system implemented in our country.

As a result of the conducted analyses and oral surveys among some local leaders and faculty students, it was found that the majority of employees who entered the faculty submitted their documents for the following reasons:

- 1) having had chronic conflicts with the leadership of local collecting bodies or other law enforcement agencies authorized to inspect activities in a supervisory manner during their service;
- 2) being unable to cope with objective and subjective difficulties in fulfilling their service obligations;
- 3) having not achieved good performance according to the results of their service evaluation and wishing to continue their work in other regional, district or capital medical institutions;
- 4) having a desire to be treated in the capital's medical institutions due to their health condition;
- 5) having not been able to receive a higher rank for several years or to be promoted to a higher position.

After graduating from the faculty, most of these students were appointed to positions equal to or lower than their previous positions by the local recruiting authorities, for some reason (the personnel department did not take into account the number of vacancies in high positions in advance or due to lack of confidence in the employee). For example, in the 2019/2020 academic year, 20 of the 50 graduates of the faculty were appointed to positions equal to or lower than their previous positions, and 3 were appointed to lower positions.

The above-mentioned negative circumstances have led to a decline in the position and status of the faculty for training leadership personnel⁹ in the Ministry of Internal Affairs system, a sharp decrease in the number of candidates who expressed a desire to acquire real leadership skills, and a lack of truly qualified leadership personnel in the Ministry of Internal Affairs system, which has led to the failure to timely resolve problematic situations in the effective organization and management of the

⁷ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" dated September 23, 2020 -No.637

⁸ Resolution No. 5076 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 15, 2021 "On measures to introduce a qualitatively new system of training professional personnel for internal affairs bodies"

⁹ Resolution No. 304 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the post-higher education system"

service, and as a result, to insufficient guarantees of reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens.

When analyzing the state of the subjects taught at this faculty, state requirements, subject programs and practical subject programs¹⁰, the academic load of the faculty students, including only classroom training sessions, amounted to an average of 50-52 academic hours per week (4 or 5 classes per day). Exceeding this load did not leave enough opportunities for students to study independently.

The academic and subject programs, practical subject programs did not sufficiently meet the requirements set out in paragraph 4.3 of the current state requirements. Some topics and subject questions in the practical subject programs of all subjects, as well as assignments for practical exercises, did not meet the requirements of the time.

In addition, the professors who have enough authority to the students of the faculty did not conduct the classes, and the situation of attracting experts with rich and practical experience from outside to the classes was also slow. Teaching methods of professors are also very old (traditional). Therefore, it is considered appropriate to create a reserve of leading personnel in the internal affairs bodies and to introduce systematic and targeted measures to train them at a professional level.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in order to train professional personnel for the internal affairs bodies, first of all, the selection of suitable personnel and quality training are of great importance. This, in turn, will lead to the strengthening of guarantees of more reliable protection of the peace and tranquility of our country and the rights and legal interests of citizens.

¹⁰ Maslov A.E., Chursin O.A. Voprosy pravovogo regulirovaniya i organizatsii professionalnoy podgotovki kadrov organov vnutrennih del po mestu sluzhby. Vestnik Moskovskogo universiteta MVD Rossii. No. 10. 2015. P. 290-292